

NATURAL COMPOSITES MATERIALS FOR STRUCTURAL AND AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Plant oils were chemically polymerized and reinforced with plant fibers such as flax and wood cellulose and used to manufacture structural panels with a foam core for housing applications. Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) process was used to make composite panels from plant oil and the different available natural fibers. Soybean based resin (Acrylated, Epoxidized Soybean Oil (AESO)) is the most common plant oil that was used and cured at room temperature. The composites were physically and mechanically tested and it was found that natural fiber reinforcement of 20 to 50 fiber weight fraction of this resin increases the flexural modulus to about 5 GPa depending on the fiber nature. The same resin reinforced with woven E-glass fiber was also tested and gave a flexural modulus of 17 GPa, while a room temperature curing of the neat resin gave a flexural modulus of just over 1 GPa. These composites were also found to behave normally at elevated temperatures.

Using this type of composite in building and automotive construction introduces great advantages such as high strength and stiffness to weight, survivability in severe weather conditions, fatigue resistance, noise suppression and design flexibility (3-dimensional formed, easy to install and structure replacement).

INTRODUCTION

The multidisciplinary ACRES (Affordable Composites from Renewable Sources) group at the University of Delaware has, for the past several years, been investigating the use of soybean triglycerides as raw materials in the synthesis of new polymers suitable for liquid molding processes. Several patent disclosures have been filed on these novel new materials.

The synthesis of structurally strong polymers from renewable resources is attractive from both the commercial and environmental perspectives and supports global sustainability. In contrast to typical petroleum-based composite matrix resins such as vinyl esters, polyesters, and epoxies, soy-based composites are optionally biodegradable; as plant oils, they contain fatty acid residues that are readily attacked by lipase-secreting bacteria. They can also be made into long-lasting, durable materials. The precedent for this research was set some 60 years ago, when Henry Ford made his first fiberglass composite

auto body using a plastic matrix derived from soybean products in 1938. Formulated with soy proteins, these materials were found to be highly resistant to impact.

The ACRES group is investigating the use of soy-based liquid molding resins reinforced with natural fibers such as hemp, chicken feathers, flax and recycled paper; and traditional glass, carbon, and synthetic fibers. To date, components made using soy-based composite resins include a hay-baler side panel, housing materials, and lightweight armor [1, 2, and 3]

MATERIALS

The materials used in this project were soybean oil based resin, natural fibers (flax, cellulose, pulp, hemp, old newspaper, recycled paper and chicken feathers), woven E-glass fiber and closed cell structural foam.

Soybean oil based Resins

Soybean oil is composed mainly of triglyceride molecules. Each triglyceride contains three fatty acid chains joined by a glycerol center. The fatty acid chains have 0-3 double bonds and vary in length from 16-22 carbon atoms. In order to produce a rigid crosslinked thermoset, the triglycerides must be functionalized. Several types of functionalization can be obtained at various active sites within the triglyceride structure: the double bond, the ester group, the allylic carbons, and the carbons alpha to the ester group. For this study, the triglycerides are first epoxidized and then reacted with acrylic acid to obtain Acrylated Epoxidized Soybean Oil (AESO), which is commercially available. The resin is then blended with a co-monomer like styrene and allowed to free radically copolymerize via redox decomposition using a metal promoter. The selection of plant oil, the optimization of the chemical functionalization and its effect on the mechanical and thermal properties of the resin, have been recently analyzed by LaScala et al. [4].

Resin was prepared using chemically modified soybean oil in the form of AESO, commercially known as Ebecryl 860 (UCB Chemicals). The AESO resin was first mixed with styrene in an optimized 2:1 weight ratio, respectively. The resin mixture was then mixed with 3 wt% initiator, Cumyl Peroxide, and 0.8 wt% catalyst, Cobalt Naphthenate. The resin was then infused into the various natural fiber mats using a vacuum infusion process as described later, and allowed to free radically copolymerize at room temperature.

Natural Fibers

Natural fibers serve as the low-cost reinforcement of the resin in biocomposites improving both the strength and stiffness of the resulting composites. Natural fibers are typically grouped into four different types: leaf, bast, fruit, and seed, depending on their source. The leaf and bast fibers are generally used in composite processing. Examples of leaf fiber include sisal, henequen, and pineapple leaf fiber (PALF). Bast fiber examples are flax, hemp, ramie, cellulose and jute. One of the major difficulties of natural fibers is that their properties are intrinsically dependant on where they are grown (locality), what part of the plant they are harvested from (leaf or stem), the maturity of the plant (age),

and how the fibers are harvested and preconditioned in a form of mats or chopped fibers, woven or unwoven. These factors result in significant variation in properties compared to their synthetic fiber counterparts (glass, aramid, and carbon). A protein based fiber mat made from chicken feathers were also used in this project as a reinforcing media [5].

Structural Foam

Elfoam, T300, manufactured by Elliott Company, Indiana was used as a core in manufacturing the structural beams in this study. The foam is closed cell polyisocyanurate that is chemically similar to but higher performing than polyurethane foam. Outstanding thermal and moisture resistance make this foam a highly effective insulating material. The foam is widely used in composite sandwich construction due to its light weight. T300 foam has a density of 2.8 lb/ft³ and operating temperature range from -297 to +300 °C.

PROCESSING AND RESULTS

Panels and Beams

VARTM was used to manufacture the composite panels, structural beams and stay-in-place bridge decking in this project. Using this process the preform was vacuum bagged on a one-sided mold as shown in Figure 1 and the resin is drawn into the preform from the top under the negative pressure created by the vacuum. Full vacuum, if reached, is equivalent to atmospheric pressure (14.7 psi or 101.3 kPa). This level of pressure may seem to be low but it is very significant when large parts are molded and this pressure is to be achieved mechanically using a body force.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing showing VARTM process

Flax fiber composites have been successfully processed, but as shown in Figure 2, flax increased the flexural modulus by only a factor of two over the neat resin (the flexural modulus of the room temperature cured neat resin was approximately 1 GPa and for flax reinforced resin was approximately 2 GPa). Composites made from recycled paper, on the other hand, increased the modulus of the room temperature cured composites to about 6 GPa.

Figure 2: Storage modulus of composites reinforced by different fibers at 37 °C. Same resin reinforced with woven E-glass fiber and cured at room Temperature gave 17 GPa.

This result, and the competitive price, made recycled paper a very attractive alternative to use in making the structural beams. Flat panels made of recycled paper were infused successfully and yielded a relatively high modulus and stiffness [1]; however, the first beam made from recycled paper was poorly infused on the bottom side and was considered a failure. This was attributed to the high density and low permeability of the paper: the fiber weight fraction of the composite panels made of recycled paper reached 55% of the total composite, as opposed to the flax weight fraction which was 23-25%. This made processing recycled paper in three dimensions much more difficult, since flow through the web of the beam was very slow, limiting the quantity of resin flowing to the bottom of the beam. To correct this problem, combinations of fibers were used: fluffy, porous fiber mats were used as shown in Figure 3, along with recycled paper to facilitate resin flow to impregnate the whole part. Figure 4 shows a natural composite beam after curing, this beam is made of flax mats and soy oil based resin and cured at room temperature. The flax beam and the recycled paper beam have been tested in bending to failure, the results of which are reported in [3]. Although the soy oil based resin and natural fiber composite has not been tested in the automotive industry, it is clear that this

resin reinforced with some natural fibers or glass fiber would be suitable for some automotive applications such as deflectors and body parts. Glass fiber reinforced soy oil based resin was tested in agricultural equipment when the ACRES group, in collaboration with the United Soybean Board and John Deere, manufactured a Round-Hay Baler, 8'x3' door panel and tested it in the field, Figure 5.

Figure 3: Schematic drawing showing the fiber preform for a recycled paper beam

Figure 4: Structural panel, natural composites and foam

Figure 5: A Round-Hay Baler, 8'x3' panel containing the name “John Deere” was made from soy-oil based resin.

Stay-in-place Bridge decking form

All natural composite material stay-in-place (SIP) bridge forms are a revolutionary idea with many potential benefits to the bridge construction industry. SIP bridge forms are corrugated sheets of material that span the distance between bridge girders. SIP forms are formwork for the concrete bridge deck and are designed to carry the dead load of the deck while the concrete cures. Before SIP forms were invented, wooden formwork was used for the same purpose, however, wooden forms are labor-intensive, requiring scaffolding to be built from ground-up and then requiring removal after the concrete has cured.

The first revolution in form design occurred when forms were made of corrugated steel to replace the wooden formwork. This was the birth of SIP forms. It occurred more than sixteen years ago, and SIP forms are widely used today. SIP forms are made of light gauge steel, and are approximately two feet (.610 meters) wide by four (1.22m) to ten (3.05m) feet long. They are screwed into angles that are welded onto bridge stringers.

Figure 6: Photograph showing infusion in progress of a stay-in-place bridge decking form

The benefits of SIP forms include speed and ease of installation, and decreased labor costs due to not removing the forms after deck curing. However, there are several disadvantages of conventional SIP forms. The first of these is that the steel pans can collect moisture, keeping it trapped between the steel and the bottom of the concrete deck. This can cause corrosion of the concrete rebar, leading to possible failure of the deck. Another problem with steel SIP forms is that the form itself prevents bridge inspectors from inspecting the bottom of the deck. The SIP form hides cracking or corrosion that can occur at the bottom of the deck. There are several advantages of a natural composite SIP form over a conventional steel form. The first of these is that the form would be able to “breathe”, or allow water to pass through and away from the concrete deck, therefore reducing the risk of corrosion. Second, the form would be biodegradable, and would break down naturally to allow bridge inspectors to examine the bottom of the deck. Finally, the forms would be lightweight compared to their steel counterparts, and would allow for faster installation and lower labor costs.

The first SIP form was made of soy oil based resin and woven E-glass fiber. The form was successfully manufactured using VARTM process (Figure 6) then was tested in three-point bending as shown in Figure 7. The elastic load-deflection curve from the test is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7: A 3-point bending test of SIP form in progress

Figure 8: 3-point bending result of SIP form

The SIP form was then tested in-situ by casting an 8 inch concrete deck on the simple supported form, as shown in Figure 9A. The form successfully withstood the concrete load and the curing process that followed. Figure 9B shows the cured concrete panel with the form.

A

B

Figure 9: The SIP form as tested by pouring concrete. A: set-up for pouring concrete, and B: the form and concrete deck.

CONCLUSIONS

Natural composite materials were successfully developed from soy oil based resin and natural fibers such as flax, cellulose and recycled paper achieving good mechanical behavior suitable for automotive and structural applications. Natural fiber reinforcement of the room temperature cured soy oil based resin increased the flexural modulus to more than 5 times the neat resin flexural modulus; woven E-glass reinforcement increased the modulus to about 17 times. Structural parts incorporating a foam core were also manufactured and tested to give the required strength for roof applications. Stay-in-place Bridge decking form was successfully manufactured and tested to replace the current in use metal form. Same material can be used as a good insulation material in housing and refrigerating trucks for transportation.

REFERENCES

1. O'Donnell, A., Dweib, M. A. and Wool, R. P., "Plant Oil-Based Resins and Natural Fiber Composites", in review, *Composites Science and Technology*, January, 2003
2. Williams, G. I., Wool, R. P., Composites from Natural Fibers and Soy Oil Resins, *Applied Composite Materials* 7: 421-432, 2000
3. Dweib, M.A., Hu, B., O'Donnell, A., Shenton, H.W., and Wool, R.P. (2003), "All-Natural Composite Sandwich Beams for Structural Applications," in review, *Composite Structures*, February 2003.
4. LaScala, J.J. and Wool R. P., "Property Analysis of Triglyceride-based Thermosets", *Macromolecules*, in press (2003)
5. Wool, R. P. and Hong, C. K., "Low Dielectric Constant Materials from Plant Oils and Chicken Feathers", Patent application No. 60/396319, 2002.